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Nucleon structure functions from a lattice Compton amplitude calculation

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Abstract

The structure of hadrons relevant for deep-inelastic scattering are completely characterised by the Compton amplitude. A direct calculation of the Compton amplitude provides a way to accessing the structure functions on the lattice, circumventing the operator mixing and renormalisation issues of the standard operator product expansion approach. In this contribution, we focus on our lattice QCD calculation of the forward Compton amplitude and highlight our progress in investigating the nucleon structure functions from first principals.

Introduction.— Understanding the internal structure of the nucleon is a long standing and intriguing subject in the field of hadron and high-energy physics. Structure functions are the essential components that encode the dynamics of the quark and gluon degrees of freedom at short distances. Calculating the structure functions from first principles is possible (see [1] for a review) but poses several challenges for lattice QCD practitioners. Traditionally, lattice calculations make use of the operator product (OPE) expansion. However, it is known that in the OPE approach, contributions of leading-twist operators are inseparably connected with the contributions from operators of higher twist, due to operator mixing and renormalisation [2].

We describe an approach that is being pursued by the QCDSF/UKQCD Collaboration, which is to directly calculate the forward Compton amplitude on the lattice in the space-like region [3]. By working with the physical amplitude, the operator mixing and renormalization issues, and the restriction to light-cone operators are circumvented. Once we are able to determine the Compton amplitude sufficiently accurately, we can expect to estimate the power corrections in structure functions, i.e. quantify the target mass corrections and estimate the contributions from higher-twist operators, which could be useful for global PDF analyses. This contribution is based on Refs. [4, 5]. Although our focus is the Compton amplitude in forward kinematics, this approach is applicable to off-forward kinematics enabling an investigation of the generalised parton distributions [6].

The Compton tensor and the moments of structure functions.— We start from the forward Compton amplitude described by the time ordered product of electromagnetic currents sandwiched between nucleon states,

$$T_{\mu\nu}(p, q) = \int d^4z e^{iqz} \rho_{ss'} \langle p, s' | \mathcal{T} \{ \mathcal{J}_\mu(z) \mathcal{J}_\nu(0) \} | p, s \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where p is the momentum and s is the spin of the nucleon, q is the momentum of the virtual photon, and ρ is the polarisation density matrix. For parity-conserving processes that involve conserved currents the spin-averaged Compton tensor is parametrised in terms of two Lorentz-invariant scalar functions, \mathcal{F}_1 , and \mathcal{F}_2 as follows

$$T_{\mu\nu}(p, q) = \left(-g_{\mu\nu} + \frac{q_\mu q_\nu}{q^2} \right) \mathcal{F}_1(\omega, Q^2) + \hat{P}_\mu \hat{P}_\nu \frac{\mathcal{F}_2(\omega, Q^2)}{p \cdot q} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{P}_\mu \equiv p_\mu - q_\mu(p \cdot q/q^2)$, with $Q^2 = -q^2$ and $\omega = 2(p \cdot q)/Q^2$.

The Compton structure functions are related to the corresponding ordinary structure functions via the optical theorem, $\text{Im} \mathcal{F}_{1,2}(\omega, Q^2) = 2\pi F_{1,2}(x, Q^2)$. Making use of analyticity, crossing symmetry and the optical theorem, we can write dispersion relations for \mathcal{F} ,

$$\overline{\mathcal{F}}_1(\omega, Q^2) = 2\omega^2 \int_0^1 dx \frac{2x F_1(x, Q^2)}{1 - x^2\omega^2 - i\epsilon}, \quad \mathcal{F}_2(\omega, Q^2) = 4\omega \int_0^1 dx \frac{F_2(x, Q^2)}{1 - x^2\omega^2 - i\epsilon}, \quad (3)$$

where $\overline{\mathcal{F}}_1(\omega, Q^2) = \mathcal{F}_1(\omega, Q^2) - \mathcal{F}_1(0, Q^2)$ is the once subtracted structure function.

Expanding the integrands in Equation (3) at fixed Q^2 as a geometric series, the Compton structure functions can be expressed as infinite sums over the Mellin moments of the inelastic structure functions,

$$\overline{\mathcal{F}}_1(\omega, Q^2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2\omega^{2n} M_{2n}^{(1)}(Q^2), \quad \text{with } M_{2n}^{(1)}(Q^2) = 2 \int_0^1 dx x^{2n-1} F_1(x, Q^2), \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_2(\omega, Q^2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 4\omega^{2n-1} M_{2n}^{(2)}(Q^2), \quad \text{with } M_{2n}^{(2)}(Q^2) = \int_0^1 dx x^{2n-2} F_2(x, Q^2). \quad (5)$$

We note that the physical moments M_{2n} that appear in Equations (4) and (5) are dominated by their leading-twist contributions, i.e. the moments of PDFs, at asymptotically large Q^2 . Finally, the unpolarised Compton structure functions \mathcal{F}_1 and \mathcal{F}_2 are accessed from the Compton tensor via,

$$\mathcal{F}_1(\omega, Q^2) = T_{33}(p, q), \quad \text{for } \mu = \nu = 3 \text{ and } p_3 = q_3 = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{F}_2(\omega, Q^2)}{\omega} = \frac{Q^2}{2E_N^2} [T_{00}(p, q) + T_{33}(p, q)], \quad \text{for } \mu = \nu = 0 \text{ and } p_3 = q_3 = q_0 = 0. \quad (7)$$

Feynman-Hellmann technique.— Our implementation of the second order Feynman-Hellmann method is presented in detail in [4]. Here, we briefly summarise its main aspects. To start, we modify the fermion action with the following perturbing term,

$$S(\lambda) = S + \lambda \int d^3z \cos(\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{z}) \mathcal{J}_\mu(\mathbf{z}), \quad (8)$$

where λ is the strength of the coupling between the quarks and the external field, $\mathcal{J}_\mu(\mathbf{z}) = Z_V \bar{q}(\mathbf{z}) \gamma_\mu q(\mathbf{z})$ is the electromagnetic current coupling to the quarks, \mathbf{q} is the external momentum inserted by the current and Z_V is the renormalization constant for the local electromagnetic current, which has been determined in Ref [7]. The perturbation is introduced on the valence quarks only, hence only quark-line connected contributions are taken into account in this work. For the perturbation of valence and sea quarks see [8].

The principal relation that we use to access the Compton amplitude is [4, 5]

$$\left. \frac{\partial^2 E_{N_\lambda}(p, q)}{\partial \lambda^2} \right|_{\lambda=0} = - \frac{T_{\mu\mu}(p, q) + T_{\mu\mu}(p, -q)}{2E_N(p)}, \quad (9)$$

where LHS is the second order energy shift calculated on the lattice, T is the Compton amplitude defined in Equation (1), $q = (0, \mathbf{q})$ is the external momentum encoded by Equation (8), and $E_{N_\lambda}(\mathbf{p})$ is the nucleon energy at momentum \mathbf{p} in the presence of a background field of strength λ . The implementation of the Feynman-Hellmann theorem described above effectively inserts an external current on to a quark line by computing its propagator with the perturbed quark action Equation (8).

Selected results and discussion.— Our simulations are carried out on QCDSF/UKQCD-generated 2 + 1-flavour gauge configurations. Two ensembles are used with volumes $V = [32^3 \times 64, 48^3 \times 96]$, and couplings $\beta = [5.50, 5.65]$ corresponding to lattice spacings $a = [0.074, 0.068]$ fm, respectively. Quark masses are tuned to the $SU(3)$ symmetric point where the masses of all three quark flavours are set to approximately the physical flavour-singlet mass, $\bar{m} = (2m_s + m_l)/3$ [9, 10], yielding $m_\pi \approx [470, 420]$ MeV. Up to $\mathcal{O}(10^4)$ and $\mathcal{O}(10^3)$ measurements are performed by employing multiple sources on the $32^3 \times 64$ and $48^3 \times 96$ ensembles, respectively.

We obtain amplitudes for several values of current momentum, Q^2 , in the range $1.5 \lesssim Q^2 \lesssim 7$ GeV². Multiple ω values are accessed at each simulated value of \mathbf{q} by varying the nucleon momentum \mathbf{p} . This analysis is performed to map out the ω dependence of the Compton structure functions given in Equations (6) and (7) for each Q^2 value that we study. The first few Mellin moments of F_1 , and F_2 are determined by performing a simultaneous fit to $\bar{\mathcal{F}}_1$ and \mathcal{F}_2 in a Bayesian framework at each Q^2 value (see Refs. [4, 5] for details). We show the lowest moments of F_2 for proton in Figure 1 as a function of Q^2 . Also shown are the experimental determinations of the Mellin moments of F_2 [11]. We see a very good agreement, although we should note that our systematics are not fully accounted for yet.

The Compton amplitude encompasses all power corrections, therefore it is possible to estimate the leading power correction (i.e. twist-4) by studying the Q^2 behaviour of the moments in a twist expansion, $M_{2,p}^{(2)}(Q^2) = M_{2,p}^{(2)} + C_{2,p}^{(2)}/Q^2 + \mathcal{O}(1/Q^4)$.

Utilising only the $M_2^{(2)}(Q^2)$ moments obtained on the $48^3 \times 96$ ensemble, we study the power corrections down to $Q^2 \approx 1.5 \text{ GeV}^2$. Our fit for proton (red band) is shown in Figure 1. The power corrections seem to become important below 5 GeV^2 . Power

Figure 1: Q^2 dependence of the lowest moments of proton F_2 . Filled stars are the experimental Mellin moments of F_2 [11]. Figure taken from [5].

corrections are a combination of target mass corrections, pure higher-twist terms, and the elastic contributions. These effects can be disentangled further, for instance by determining the elastic contributions from form factors [12, 13], and employing Nachtmann moments [14] to account for the target mass corrections, along with including the logarithmic evolution of the moments. We leave such an investigation to a future work.

Summary and outlook.— With the Compton amplitude approach it is possible to directly investigate the structure functions including the effects beyond leading twist. We showed the versatility of this approach by calculating the moments of transverse structure function, F_2 , along with their Q^2 dependence. This allows us to study the physical power corrections in a lattice calculation.

Currently our calculations involve configurations with two different lattice spacings and volumes, all at the $SU(3)$ symmetric point. Calculations on additional ensembles that cover a range of lattice spacings and pion masses are required to fully account for systematic effects and make contact to the phenomenology.

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